

Reactions of Carbonylchlorohydridotris(triphenylphosphine)ruthenium(II) with some Aromatic Thioamides

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During the recent years much interest has been shown in the synthesis of metal chelates with ligands containing thioamide groups due to their different biological application¹. It has, however, been reported that on complexation the activity of ligands increases further. The ligands RCSNHCOR' have been recently used in the preparation of various transition metal complexes with interesting properties². All of these ligands have been found to behave as bidentate or monodentate coordinating through sulphur or nitrogen. In this paper, we describe the synthesis and characterisation of the products of reaction of RCSNHCOR' with RuHCOCI(PPh₃)₃.

The ligands reported here are as follows : (R=2-pyrrole, R'=OC₂H₅) *N*-ethoxycarbonylpyrrole-2-thiocarboxamide (ETH) ; (R=2-thiophene, R'=

OC₂H₅) *N*-ethoxycarbonylthiophene-2-thiocarboxamide (EPH) ; (R=2-pyrrole, R'=NHPH) *N*-phenylcarbamoyl pyrrole-2-thiocarboxamide (PTH) ; (R=2-thiophene, R'=NHPH) *N*-phenylcarbamoylthiophene-2-thiocarboxamide (PPTH).

Results and Discussion

The complexes are air-stable and soluble in most of the organic solvents. Assuming that the metal ion adopts normally preferred geometry in their complexes, the analytical data (Table 1) are suggestive of the stoichiometry proposed for the complexes. The ligands can function either as neutral or anionic with sulphur, nitrogen and oxygen as potential donor atoms. In case bonding of the ligands with metal ion takes place through sulphur and oxygen, their behaviour might parallel the extensively studied monothio- β -diketones. However, due to weaker acidic nature of the hydrogen atom bonded to the relatively more electronegative nitrogen atom of RCSNHCOR' moiety, it could possibly be that the nature of the complexes may be different from those of monothio- β -diketones.

All the ligands contain thioamide group and

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analyses % : Found/(Calcd.)							M.p. °C
		Ru	Cl	S	P	C	H	N	
[RuHCICO(ETH)(PPh ₃) ₃]	Yellowish brown	10.35 (10.38)	4.10 (4.00)	3.55 (3.60)	6.76 (6.98)	60.52 (60.84)	4.50 (4.62)	4.10 (3.15)	210
[RuHCICO(EPH)(PPh ₃) ₂]	Brown	11.20 (11.16)	3.80 (3.92)	7.18 (7.07)	6.50 (6.85)	59.55 (59.70)	4.38 (4.42)	1.44 (1.54)	180
[RuHCICO(PTH)(PPh ₃) ₂]	Raddish brown	10.60 (10.80)	3.84 (3.79)	3.56 (3.42)	6.75 (6.63)	62.56 (62.92)	4.64 (4.49)	4.38 (4.49)	240
[RuHCICO(PPTH)(PPh ₃) ₂]	Light brown	10.48 (10.61)	3.62 (3.73)	6.58 (6.73)	6.36 (6.51)	61.50 (61.79)	4.46 (4.30)	2.84 (2.94)	220

give rise to four characteristic thioamide bands I, II, III and IV i.e. $\delta_{N-H} + \nu_{C-N}$, $\nu_{C-S} + \nu_{C-N}$ + δ_{C-H} , $\nu_{C-N} + \nu_{C-S}$, ν_{C-S} respectively in the region 1550–760 cm^{-1} (Table 2). In case of coordination of the ligand through its thiocarbonyl sulphur atom, the ν_{C-S} and thioamide band IV should shift to lower wavenumber and thioamide band I should shift to a higher wave number³, whereas, if coordination is through the N atom, the thioamide band I will shift to a lower wavenumber. Coordination through carbonyl group is ruled out because in all the cases $\nu_{C=O}$ band is shifted to higher wavenumber. Further, it is highly unlikely for oxygen atom of (OEt) to participate in the complex formation. Coordination through ring nitrogen or sulphur of pyrrole and thiophene is unlikely due to their weakly basic nature. The thioamide bands II and III⁴ do not shift systematically (max. shift ± 10) after complexation hence could not be used reasonably for deciding a bonding site. All the characteristic bands of PPh_3 , CO(carbonyl) RuH have been observed in the spectra of complexes⁵.

methods⁷. All the chemicals used were either AnalaR or chemically pure grade. Solvents were dried before use. All the reactions were carried out under dry N_2 . The light petroleum used had b.p. 60–80°.

Sulphur, chloride and phosphorus were estimated gravimetrically. C, H and N analyses were done at Microanalytical Laboratory, I.I.T., Kanpur. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 580 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (CHCl_3) on a Shimadzu UV 190 spectrophotometer. Melting points were determined on a Fisher-John melting point apparatus.

A solution of the ligand (~ 0.2 g) in benzene (10 ml) was added slowly to a continuously stirred solution of $[\text{RuHClCO}(\text{PPh}_3)_3]$ (~ 0.15 g in 10 ml) in benzene under N_2 -atmosphere. The mixture was refluxed for 30 min, then allowed to cool and the resulting solid was washed with alcohol and petroleum ether and dried under reduced pressure.

TABLE 2—MAJOR IR BANDS (cm^{-1}) OF LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES

Compd.	ν_{NH}	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=S}}$	Thioamide Bands				$\nu_{\text{Ru-H}}$	Mode of coordination
				I	II	III	IV		
ETH	3 360s 3 140m	1 740s	1 120s	1 550m	1 300m	1 120m	865m	—	—
$[\text{RuHClCO}(\text{ETH})(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$	3 360m 3 140m	1 750s	1 105s	1 560m	1 290m	1 010m	855m	1 900m	S
EPH	3 245m	1 730s	1 180s	1 510m	1 355s	1 020s	770s	—	—
$[\text{RuHClCO}(\text{EPH})(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$	3 230s	1 740s	1 180s	1 490s	1 360s	1 010m	760s	1 906w	N
PTH	3 410s 3 260m 3 160m	1 720s	1 125s	1 520s	1 350s	1 000w	800w	—	—
$[\text{RuHClCO}(\text{PTH})(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$	3 400w 3 270w 3 165m	1 720s	1 110m	1 570s	1 340m	1 010m	780m	1 905w	S
PPTH	3 260s	1 690s	1 180s	1 500m	1 380m	1 010s	760s	—	—
$[\text{RuHClCO}(\text{PPTH})(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$	3 240s	1 700s	1 180s	1 500m	1 390m	1 020s	750s	1 900m	N

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The new bands of medium intensity at 370–490 cm^{-1} may be assigned to couple vibration of $\nu_{\text{Ru-Cl}} + \nu_{\text{Ru-S}}$ or $\nu_{\text{Ru-N}}$ ⁶.

All the complexes are diamagnetic indicating spin-pairing in Ru^{II} (d^6 -system) and hence a distorted octahedral geometry could be assigned to these complexes.

The ground state of Ru^{II} in octahedral environment is $^1A_{1g}$ and hence only two spin-allowed transitions $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g}$ or $^1T_{2g}$ are expected. The bands at 500–520 and 460–490 nm in all the complexes are assigned to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{2g}$ respectively and all other transition are due to intraligand and charge transfer band.

Thus a distorted octahedral geometry could be proposed to all the four complexes.

Experimental

The ligands were prepared by the reported